

UP2030

Urban Planning and design ready for 2030

D3.4 – Bundle of Digital Twins tools for net zero decision-making 1

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About UP2030:

UP2030 is dedicated to aiding cities in achieving climate neutrality through enhanced urban planning and design. The project introduces the innovative 5UP approach to support city stakeholders and local authorities in integrating climate-neutral strategies into their everyday actions and long-term planning. Focused on promoting spatial justice and inclusive participation, UP2030 empowers communities and local governments to become agents of change, driving socio-technical transitions that enhance urban liveability and sustainability. The project's strategy aims to produce actionable insights and scalable solutions for urban environments, prioritizing resilience, equity, and sustainable urban development.

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Abstract	<p>As part of the transition to clean energy systems and decarbonisation, it's crucial for urban planners and developers to understand current energy demand to help transform cities into resilient, sustainable areas. This report introduces the first version of digital tools created under Task 3.2, "Digital Twins of Urban Environments for Energy Integration and GHG Emissions Reduction," within the UP2030 Project. These tools are designed to help cities to simulate energy baselines and assess the environmental impacts of efficiency measures over time. An integration framework has been developed to streamline data acquisition and maximise the effectiveness of these tools, detailed in Chapter 3. The integration framework has been built considering the main functionalities of each tool, which include robust energy models, standard energy demand profiles, thermal refurbishment assessments, and user-friendly visualisation capabilities. Communication protocols are being established to ensure seamless integration.</p> <p>The report also outlines the plan for prototyping these tools in various cities, as described in Chapter 5. Key findings from the first phase indicate that the digital tools are currently in testing and are expected to be fully operational by September 2024. The innovations in these tools range from technical improvements to enhanced predictive models and better user interfaces, all aimed at providing comprehensive digital twins for cities. These tools are</p>			

essential for creating effective decarbonisation and climate mitigation strategies, helping cities move towards Net-Zero or PositiveEnergy Districts.

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Executive summary

In the context of the decarbonisation and the transition to clean energy systems, stakeholders engaged in strategic planning and urban development needs to provide themselves with information related to current energy demand. This enables them to contextualise the potential transformation of urban environments into more resilient and sustainable areas. However, the implementation of efficiency measures inevitably impacts greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions.

This document represents the first version of the digital tool’s solutions developed under the Task 3.2 “Digital Twins of Urban environments for energy integration and GHG emissions reduction” and highlighting the progress made in the first phase of the UP2030 Project. Thus, the objective of this deliverable is to provide pertinent stakeholders (cities) with comprehensive insights into the tools developed for simulating energy baselines and estimating environmental impacts through efficiency measures (life cycle assessments) across various time frames (refer to Chapters 2 and 4).

Moreover, to streamline data acquisition and leverage the unique features of each tool, an integration framework has been devised. The framework detailed in Chapter 3 establishes data flows to maximize the outcomes of the tools. Finally, the document outlines the workplan for the development of a prototype in cities in Chapter 0.

Overall, this deliverable aims to elucidate the added value that digital tools can offer to end-users and provides guidance on interpreting the results. Such comprehension is crucial for devising decarbonisation and climate mitigation roadmaps aimed at achieving Net-Zero or Positive Energy Districts.

Content alignment with other UP2030 deliverables

The UP2030 project fosters exchange and cooperation among partners and deliverables beyond the work package’s structure. Therefore, the content of this document has been developed in alignment with METU/GUNAM, MAG and ETH within WP3. The following table lists the deliverables and milestones that were input for this document and the upcoming ones that could benefit from the content here presented.

Input from	Contributes to
D3.1 Transformative Pathways Roadmaps: Strategic Integration of Solutions and Interoperability 1	D3.2 Transformative Pathways Roadmaps: Strategic Integration of Solutions and Interoperability 2 D5.4 Guidelines for economic valuations & assessment of financial instruments for spatial interventions 1 D3.5 Bundle of digital twin tools for net zero decision-making 2
Mil 7 Cities establish user stories.	Mil 13 All cities have at least one successful prototype

The recipients of this deliverable's content are key stakeholders in cities engaged in strategic planning and liaisons within the UP2030 Project, as it serves as a functional guideline on tools developed under Net-Zero Urban Districts. Updated version including results obtained in tools testing in cities will be the second version which is due on M36. This deliverable provides useful information to cities and liaisons for the Action Phase of the project, containing the data required for using the tools and an overview of the results provided for each tool and the bundle itself for developing the decarbonisation and climate mitigation plan in urban districts. Finally, this is not the final version of the bundle of Digital Twin tools but represents the work completed up to M18 of the project, so dissemination options are not expected until the consolidation of the bundle is finalised.

Acronyms

Please add all the acronyms mentioned in the document in alphabetical order.

Acronym	Full name
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BIM	Building Information Model
CO ₂	Carbon Dioxide
D	Deliverable
DoA	Description of Action
e-mobility	Electric Mobility
EPBD	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive
EU	European Union
EVs	Electric Vehicles
GHG	Greenhouse gases emissions
HVAC	Heating, ventilation, and air conditioning
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
M	Month
MAG	MAGGIOLI
MFA	Material Flow Analysis
m ²	Squared meters
Mil	Milestone
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
PV	Photovoltaics
T	Task
WP	Work package

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The primary purpose of this deliverable is to equip stakeholders—specifically city planners and urban developers—involved in the UP2030 Project with advanced digital tools designed for simulating energy demand and assessing environmental impacts. These tools are intended to support the transition of urban areas into resilient, sustainable, and Net-Zero or Positive Energy Districts. By providing detailed insights into energy integration and greenhouse gas emissions reduction, this document aims to guide stakeholders through the initial phase of employing these tools, thereby facilitating strategic planning and execution towards decarbonization and climate mitigation goals.

The scope of this deliverable encompasses an integration framework that details data flows between digital tools to enhance their effectiveness and interoperability, alongside comprehensive descriptions of various simulation scenarios such as Buildings Retrofitting, Integration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES), Integration of Storage Systems, Integration of Mobility Assets, and Renovation of Energy Systems. These scenarios include specific data requirements for accurate simulations, ensuring stakeholders can prepare and collect the requisite information, and underlying assumptions made within the simulations to provide context and boundaries for the interpretations of the results. It provides a step-by-step guide for using the developed tools, ensuring stakeholders can maximize their utility and accurately interpret results. Additionally, the deliverable discusses each tool individually, highlighting barriers encountered and lessons learned during the project's first phase, thereby setting a foundational basis for continuous improvement. Finally, it outlines a future roadmap for the ongoing development and refinement of the tools, aligning with the broader objectives of the UP2030 Project and facilitating further integration into urban planning processes.

1.2 Document Structure

The document is organised as follows:

- ❖ Section 1 - Introduction: description of the purpose and scope of the document and its structure
- ❖ Section 2 - Tools for Net-Zero Strategies: Addressing Specific Challenges: explanation of the obstacle/barrier/challenge that is being covered by the tool that each partner is developing.
- ❖ Section 3 - Integration framework: Maximising the benefit from tools users: description of integration framework and data flows between tools
- ❖ Section 4 - Scenarios proposal for Strategic Urban Planning: description of data requirements for simulation, assumptions, and results interpretation
- ❖ Section 5 - Next Steps: description of step-by-step procedure to use the tools.
- ❖ Section 6 - Barriers and Lessons Learnt: description of barriers and lessons learned during this first phase of the project.
- ❖ Section 7 - Conclusions.

2 Tools for Net-Zero Strategies: Addressing Specific Challenges

Buildings account for about 40% of total energy use in the European Union (EU). In alignment with the EU Directive 2010/31/EU¹, there is a critical need to lower this consumption significantly. Furthermore, the Buildings Directive (2018/844/EU)² introduced new specifications for both the current building stock and new constructions. Firstly, member states must establish and implement minimum energy performance requirements at the building level, inspect the energy systems supplying that energy, and propose new long-term renovation plans with the goal of decarbonizing the building stock by 2050, with certain milestones set for 2030, 2040, and 2050, specifically Net-Zero objectives focus on reducing the net greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions of cities to zero. This involves enhancing energy efficiency, integrating RES, and adopting sustainable building practices, specific objectives and documentation must be included in the energy and climate plans of each member state.

Optimising energy across an entire city presents a significant technical challenge due to the intricate nature of urban systems. Innovative strategies are essential for managing this complexity effectively. Segmenting cities into districts and evaluating their decarbonisation potential is a promising approach because it reduces the technical complexity related to optimising energy use and flows in a defined area. Also, this method addresses challenges related to local context, incentives, social factors, regulatory frameworks, and market readiness.

However, recent studies have shown that most cities are not digitally ready to analyse and diagnose the current energy situation beyond large figures such as final energy consumption in the residential sector. Therefore, the first focus of the stakeholders involved in city decision-making is to digitalise and develop solutions to make cities smart. This approach will enable the rapid acquisition of data, allowing them to evaluate the baseline and determine areas of significant energy intensity for the prioritisation of actions, as well as the development of tailor-made strategies at the district (Kılış et al., 2024; Salvia et al., 2021; Ulpiani et al., 2023).

Within the framework of the UP2030 project, digital tools have been developed to contribute to the creation of programmes and strategies for mitigating environmental impact in urban settings through the calculation of Direct GHG emissions (Scope 1).

- Building Information Model (BIM) Module and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) developed by CIRCE.
- Artificial intelligence (AI) powered toolset for the decarbonisation of building & transport solutions developed and co-created by METU and GUNAM.
- MIRA solution for Cities as Digital Twins solution developed by MAGGIOLI (MAG).
- Circular Urban Planning tool proposed by ETH.

In the next sub-sections, tools developed are described in more detail.

¹ Directive 2010/31/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 19 May 2010 on the energy performance of buildings.

² Directive (EU) 2018/844 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 30 May 2018 amending Directive 2010/31/EU on the energy performance of buildings and Directive 2012/27/EU on energy efficiency.

2.1 Building Information Model (BIM) Module and Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)

A review of the state of the art in building digitalisation in urban environments reveals that approximately 2% of publications in recent years related to "Smart Buildings" are associated with the development of Digital Twins, and of those, 33% are related to the integration of BIMs for analysing the building's energy performance (31 article publications). However, it has been found that one of the barriers is the use of the information and construction characteristics contained in the BIM with simulations to obtain the building's energy performance is the different scales of BIM files due different buildings smart readiness indicator (SRI) levels that may affect the energy simulations because energy modules are based in specific parameters that a BIM file can contain or not depending of the SRI of the building. On the other hand, estimating thermal energy consumption at finer granularities (Hourly based) and obtaining energy consumption profiles is another key challenge to overcome in this regard (Hernández et al., 2024).

The BIM Module and LCA tools are designed to address the complex challenges of reducing GHG emissions and achieving Net-Zero energy statuses in urban districts.

This tool facilitates the current assessment for the optimization of the building envelope in terms of thermal transmittance and evaluates its impact and that of residential energy systems by exploiting detailed modelling and environmental impact analysis. It plays a crucial role for city councils and municipalities in monitoring and managing carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions and energy consumption across different districts, encompassing buildings and the renovation of building energy systems. By providing detailed projections for future scenarios in 2030 and 2050, the tool aids in the strategic planning and implementation of sustainable interventions. This enables local governments to make informed decisions that align with their long-term environmental targets and sustainability goals, ensuring effective adaptation to climate change and progress toward Net-Zero objectives.

This tool helps in this endeavour by providing a detailed analysis of the thermal performance of building envelopes and the environmental impact of renovating residential energy systems. By optimising building designs to improve thermal transmittance, the tool helps to reduce the energy required for heating and cooling, which is a significant component of a building's total energy consumption.

BIM modules enable the acquisition of the constructive characteristics of existing buildings, making them useful and powerful tools for evaluating the environmental impacts associated with building refurbishments, as well as energy models related to heating, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) consumption. The current objective is to achieve digital twins based on the information contained in BIMs. However, a BIM can have different levels of detail depending on the visualisation and the information it contains (Nawrocka et al., 2023; Zhu & Wu, 2022). The innovation of this tool lies in enhancing the level of detail that can result from a BIM file through the integration of the energy model on an hourly basis and its potential use as a building renovation tool to estimate energy savings associated with ensuring thermal comfort.

The main barrier to overcome during this first phase project is the lack of the expected data from the cities. The task description in the description of action (DoA) assumed that the cities already had **existing digital twins**. Therefore, the task's approach involved integrating an energy model and lifecycle analysis of the buildings themselves. However, it was found that the cities did not have BIM files for the buildings in the selected districts. As a result, the scope of the tool was modified while still achieving the same objectives. If BIM files are available, it will be extracted the construction data from them. If not, templates have been developed for acquiring the minimum required data. Accordingly, the data required to run the simulations are listed below. This allows the cities to assess whether their digital twins/BIM contain this information and can provide it, or if it will be needed to complete the template that will be provided by CIRCE.

2.1.1 Technical requirements

To ensure easy reference, it is important to provide a concise summary of the technical aspects. The following table outlines the technical requirements for the BIM Module and LCA - CIRCE, including details on versioning information, licensing, documentation, and the programming language used.

Table 1. Technical aspects of the BIM Module and LCA - CIRCE

Technical Aspect	Description
Versioning information	Tool is being developed from scratch within the project. The energy module is fully developed. The scope of the LCA was defined and is in the process of being automated and integrated with the energy modules.
License	TBD
Online-documentation	To be created
Programming Language	Python

The information that the BIM files should contain is described in Table 2 below. However, a questionnaire has been developed in case the pilot sites do not have the files.

Table 2. CIRCE common information data requirements for the tool

Common information	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit/Type
Location	<i>LocCountry</i>	Name of the country	-
Location	<i>LocCity</i>	Name of the city	-
Location	<i>LocCoordinates</i>	Latitude, longitude, altitude	°, °, m
Climatic Zone	<i>CZone</i>	Type of climatic zone A, B, C, D, E, alpha	-
Building information	<i>Building</i>	Residential or other, select option	-
Building information	<i>nR</i>	Number of residential buildings they have	integer
Building information	<i>YearR</i>	Age of the residential building, year of construction	Years, integer
Building information	<i>nO</i>	Number of commercial/hospital/Restaurant/other buildings they have	integer

Building information	<i>YearO</i>	Age of the other types of building, year of construction	Years, integer
Building information	<i>WeeklyS</i>	Weekly schedule (1) Monday to Friday (2) Monday to Sunday (3) Weekends Other: Please specify	-
Building information	<i>Openingh</i>	Opening hours XX:XX format	Hours (h)
Building information	<i>Closingh</i>	Opening hours XX:XX format	h
Surfaces	<i>Roof</i>	Roof Area	Squared meters (m2), integer
Surfaces	<i>Wall</i>	Wall Area	m2, integer
Surfaces	<i>Openings</i>	Windows Area	m2, integer
Thermal data	<i>Uwall</i>	Current thermal transmittance of wall (Optional)	W/m2K
Thermal data	<i>Uroof</i>	Current thermal transmittance of roof (Optional)	W/m2K
Thermal data	<i>Uwindow</i>	Current thermal transmittance of window (Optional)	W/m2K

2.1.2 Outputs of the Tool

Table 3 shows the outputs that users will obtain from using the tool developed. These include calculations of heating and cooling energy consumption. These calculations consider the current situation, retrofit scenarios, and climate change impact, with projections for 2030 and 2050 based on climate profiles and expected increase in temperatures.

Table 3. CIRCE outputs of the tool

Outputs	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit
Energy demand profile	<i>Qbaseline</i>	Hourly baseline HVAC energy consumed by the building	kWh
Energy demand profile	<i>Qoptimal</i>	Hourly optimal HVAC energy consumed by the building	kWh
GHG emissions	<i>tCO2baseline</i>	Total baseline GHG emissions	t

GHG emissions	<i>tCO₂optimal</i>	Total optimal GHG emissions	t
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2.2 [AI-powered toolset for the decarbonisation of building & transport solution](#)

For cities to achieve carbon neutrality, decarbonisation of buildings, which are among the primary consumers of energy in urban areas, is essential. This can only be achieved through a transition to clean (renewable) energy. Particularly, the aging building stock exhibits low energy performance and thus requires retrofitting. Not only does energy performance matter, but these buildings are also expected to negatively affect occupant comfort as the impacts of climate change intensify. Another major contributor to carbon emissions in cities is transportation. Large cities face severe traffic congestion and overcrowd public transportation. To reduce carbon emissions from urban transportation, the use of clean-energy-powered electric mobility (e-mobility) should be expanded to decrease the volume of traffic caused by individual vehicle use and to ensure accessible mobility for everyone. The impact of these actions in the building and transportation sectors on carbon emissions should be analysed with digital tools. As a solution, we aim to develop a data-driven, integrated tool to aid in the decarbonization of cities through modelling, simulation, and AI-based prediction of the performance of the building stock and electric vehicles (EVs). We particularly focus on the effective use of photovoltaic (PV) systems in urban energy systems to reduce CO₂ emissions, improve air quality, lower energy costs, and reduce traffic congestion.

The objective of the tool is to support decision-making for carbon neutrality of cities by considering building energy use reductions, on-site renewable energy production (particularly PVs), and electric micro-mobility in an integrated way. As such, the tool addresses urban challenges, including high CO₂ emissions due to buildings and traffic, aging building stock that has low energy and thermal performance, severe traffic congestion and overcrowded public transport, high and energy costs, as well as some social challenges including energy poverty and indoor overheating related health risks. In this regard, the tool utilises deep learning and other machine learning approaches in the following four modules: Module 1 supports the calculation of climate change impact on building energy use/occupant comfort for years 2020 and 2050, and the exploration of different building energy retrofit options by utilizing deep learning approaches. Module 2 allows the automated calculation of electric energy to be generated by rooftop solar panels. Module 3 helps users determine the optimal locations of PV-integrated e-scooter charging stations using existing travel data. Module 4 helps to conduct feasibility analyses for the integration of real-time control of micro-e-mobility (e-bike and/or e-scooter) and PV electricity generation co-deployment.

Promoting e-mobility aligns with net-zero strategies by reducing emissions from conventional vehicles. The strategic placement of PV-powered charging stations and the integration of real-time control systems for electric micro-mobility contribute to a more sustainable urban transport network, reducing overall carbon emissions. Net-zero requires a systematic approach, considering all sources of emissions and their interconnections. The problem we described above, and the solution our tool provides present a holistic and systematic approach to achieving Net-Zero strategies.

2.2.1 [Technical requirements](#)

The table below summarizes the technical aspects of the AI-powered toolset for decarbonising buildings and transport. It includes details on the technology's current state, development plans, and key components, such as energy modelling, machine learning predictions, and previous implementations in two Turkish neighbourhoods.

Table 4. Technical aspects of the AI-powered toolset for the decarbonisation of buildings & transport solution - GUNAM

Technical Aspect	Description
Versioning information	This technology is going to be developed within the project. Parts of it (energy modelling and simulation-based analysis of building energy performance calculation, and machine learning based prediction) have been developed previously and implemented for two other neighbourhoods in Turkey.
License	TBD
Online-documentation	TBD
Programming Language	Python for machine learning, EnergyPlus for building energy modelling, PVWatts for PV modelling

Table 5 provides a detailed overview of the data requirements for Module 1 of the GUNAM project, categorizing the necessary information into geometric, semantic, and climate data. The table's content is more detailed than the CIRCE data requirements.

Table 5. GUNAM data Requirements for Module 1

Module 1	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit
Geometric Data	<i>bldlayout</i>	Footprints of building	m ²
Geometric Data	<i>bldgheight</i>	The height of the building	m
Geometric Data	<i>zonedivision</i>	Information about how each building is divided to zones	-
Semantic Data	<i>U_{wall}</i>	Thermal transmittance of wall	W/m ² K
Semantic Data	<i>U_{roof}</i>	Thermal transmittance of roof	W/m ² K
Semantic Data	<i>U_{ground}</i>	Thermal transmittance of ground	W/m ² K
Semantic Data	<i>U_{window}</i>	Thermal transmittance of window	W/m ² K
Semantic Data	<i>wwr_N</i>	Window to wall ratio in north direction	%
Semantic Data	<i>wwr_W</i>	Window to wall ratio in west direction	%
Semantic Data	<i>wwr_S</i>	Window to wall ratio in south direction	%
Semantic Data	<i>wwr_E</i>	Window to wall ratio in east direction	%

Semantic Data	PPL	Number of people per square meter	people/m ²
Semantic Data	η_{boiler}	The efficiency of boiler	%
Semantic Data	<i>Infiltration</i>	The ratio of air leakage	ACH
Semantic Data	$SHGC$	Solar heat gain coefficient of window	-
Semantic Data	LPD	Lighting power density	W/m ²
Semantic Data	EPD	Equipment power density	W/m ²
Semantic Data	$T_{heating}$	The heating set point for thermostat	°C
Semantic Data	SE_N	The visible sky ratio from north direction (calculated from energy models)	%
Semantic Data	SE_W	The visible sky ratio from west direction (calculated from energy models)	%
Semantic Data	SE_S	The visible sky ratio from south direction (calculated from energy models)	%
Semantic Data	SE_E	The visible sky ratio from east direction (calculated from energy models)	%
Climate Data	$T_{outside}$	Dry bulb temperature	°C
Climate Data	HDD	Heating degree days	°C
Climate Data	CDD	Cooling degree days	°C
Climate Data	GHR	Global horizontal radiation	W/m ²

Table 6 provides a detailed overview of the data requirements for Module 2 of the GUNAM project, categorizing the necessary information into panel related, shading related, and climate data. The table's content is more detailed than the CIRCE data requirements.

Table 6. GUNAM data Requirements for Module 2

Module 2	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit
Panel related	<i>Panel_efficiency</i>	The percentage of incident solar energy that is converted to electricity	%
Panel related	<i>Panel_area</i>	The area of the PV surfaces	m ²
Panel related	<i>Age</i>	The age of the PV panels	-

Panel related	<i>Panel_tilt</i>	The slope angle at which solar panels are mounted to face the sun	°
Panel related	<i>Panel_azimuth</i>	The angle between the projection of sun rays and a line due south or north	°
Shading related	<i>Annual shading</i>	Thermal transmittance of wall	W/m ² K
Climate Data	<i>Dry_bulb_aver</i>	Average of dry bulb temperature	°C
Climate Data	<i>HDD</i>	Heating degree days	°C
Climate Data	<i>CDD</i>	Cooling degree days	°C
Climate Data	<i>GHR_aver</i>	Average of global horizontal radiation	W/m ²

Table 7 provides a detailed overview of the data requirements for Module 3 of the GUNAM project, categorizing the necessary information into building, PV and mobility related. The table's content is more detailed than the CIRCE data requirements.

Table 7. GUNAM data Requirements for Module 3

Module 3	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit
Building related	<i>Building coordinates</i>	The coordinate points of each building	°, °, m
Building related	<i>Qelectricity</i>	Electricity energy consumption of buildings	kWh/m ²
PV related	<i>Qelecproduction</i>	Electricity energy production from PV	kWh/m ²
Mobility related	<i>start_loc</i>	The starting point of each drive	°, °, m
Mobility related	<i>end_loc</i>	The end point of each drive	°, °, m

2.2.2 Outputs of the Tool

Table 8 shows the outputs of the tool obtained from different modules of the tool. The outputs of Module 1 include calculations of heating and cooling energy consumption, electrical energy consumption for lighting and equipment, and the degree of indoor overheating. These calculations consider the current situation, retrofit scenarios, and climate change impact, with projections for 2020 and 2050. This approach enables cities to quantitatively assess the effects of their retrofit decisions on building energy performance and occupant comfort for both present and future climates. Furthermore, it facilitates the mathematical quantification of carbon emissions resulting from these decisions, incorporating considerations of climate change. Module 2 generates outputs related to the solar PV energy production from the rooftops of buildings. By employing this module, cities can mathematically determine the potential energy yield from installed PV systems on building rooftops with resolutions that can be hourly, monthly, or annually. The output of Module 3 is the strategic placement of PV-powered e-mobility charging stations. Cities aiming to expand their e-mobility infrastructure and optimise it based on RES and logistical considerations can

utilise this optimisation model. The model provides guidance on the placement of new charging stations based on renewable energy availability and the geographical distribution of stations.

Table 8. GUNAM outputs of the tool

Outputs	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit
Building related	<i>Qheating</i>	Total annual heating energy consumption of the building	kWh/m ²
Building related	<i>Qcooling</i>	Total annual cooling energy consumption of the building	kWh/m ²
Building related	<i>Qlighting</i>	Total annual lighting energy consumption of the building	kWh/m ²
Building related	<i>Qequipment</i>	Total annual equipment energy consumption of the building	kWh/m ²
Building related	<i>IOD</i>	Indoor overheating degree	° C
PV related	<i>Q_{PV}</i>	Electricity energy production from PV (hourly and annual)	kWh/m ²
Mobility related	<i>(x_{loc}, y_{loc})</i>	The coordinates of the charging stations	°, °, m

2.3 MIRA solution for Cities as Digital Twins solution

Digital twin is a cutting-edge technology solution designed to create, manage, and utilize digital replicas of physical systems and processes. Digital twins are virtual models that mirror the characteristics, behaviours, and real-time status of their physical counterparts. MIRA stands out in this realm by offering a comprehensive suite of tools and capabilities that cater to a variety of industries, including manufacturing, healthcare, urban planning, energy, mobility and more.

MIRA as a digital twin tool provides cities with the ability to create virtual replicas of urban environments. These replicas allow city planners and officials to simulate various scenarios, optimize infrastructure, and enhance decision-making processes. Digital twins enable efficient urban planning, helping to design better transportation systems, allocate resources effectively, and prepare for emergencies. By integrating real-time data from sensors, they facilitate proactive maintenance of critical infrastructure, extending its lifespan and reducing costs. Furthermore, digital twins foster citizen engagement by providing interactive platforms for residents to explore and contribute to urban development projects. They also support sustainability efforts by analysing environmental data and aiding in the implementation of eco-friendly policies. Overall, digital twin tools offer cities a powerful means to improve efficiency, resilience, and citizen satisfaction in the face of complex urban challenges.

For the purposes of UP2030, this tool goes beyond assessing the impact of building materials by integrating energy storage, energy systems renovation, PV installation, and mobility integration into its simulations. It allows users to visualize pilot locations and predict future energy demands for both 2030 and 2050 under

optimal scenarios. Users can observe the potential energy savings and reductions in greenhouse gas emissions through intuitive graphs and charts.

MIRA acts also as a point of entry for users, an input for ingesting data and a visualization platform for data and analytics produced by other tools in the bundle.

2.3.1 Technical requirements

MIRA is a cloud-based platform, directly accessible through a web browser for registered users. No extra software is required for the end user. It is currently used in industrial environments and is functioning as a working prototype for city/area digital twin visualization.

Table 9. Technical Requirements for MIRA tool - MAG

Technical Aspect	Description
Versioning information	V2.4 Working prototype of most required functionalities.
License	Commercial
Online-documentation	To be delivered
Programming aspects	
Framework	Angular
Database language	Postgres
Graph database management system	Neo4j

Technical Specifications of the MIRA Digital Twins Platform

- **Real-Time Data Integration:** MIRA integrates seamlessly with IoT devices, sensors, and other data sources to gather real-time information. This continuous data flow ensures that the digital twin remains an up-to-date reflection of the physical entity. Real-time integration enables proactive monitoring, predictive maintenance, and immediate response to anomalies.
- **Scalability and Flexibility:** MIRA is designed to be highly scalable, accommodating everything from small projects to large, complex systems. Its flexibility allows for customization to meet specific industry or urban requirements and to adapt as those requirements evolve over time.
- **Visualization and User Interface:** Users can interact with models of their digital twins, which enhances understanding and facilitates decision-making. The intuitive user interface is designed to be user-friendly, making it accessible to both technical and non-technical users.
- **Integration with Existing Systems:** MIRA can be integrated with existing systems such as analytics tools, IoT data streams and other specialized software.

2.3.2 Outputs of the tool

MIRA provides several outputs tailored to each separate use case. An initial map with the location of IoT sensors, buildings/areas allow the user to have an overview of the assets/areas monitored (See Figure 1). Customisable dashboards concentrate and visualise key indicators produced by data analytics and third-

party tools. Furthermore, users can create personalised dashboards, using widgets and layouts that suit their specific needs.

The main outputs of the platform aim to provide helpful information for designing Net-zero districts and cities. These outputs include graphs and charts for energy demand, energy saved, CO₂ saved, accumulated energy consumption, energy, and CO₂ savings by action (PV installation, renovations etc.), identification of buildings with potential for maximum savings in CO₂ and more.

Figure 1 MIRA User interface visualisation

2.4 Circular Urban Planning

The initial scope of the tool development aimed to create a digital platform for circular construction by integrating circularity assessment metrics into the LCA+Material Flow Analysis (MAF)+GIS modelling framework. This tool was to be adapted and tested on a Swiss case study at an urban scale. Further research would be necessary to adapt this tool for specific case studies in other countries, such as a neighbourhood in Turkey or Thessaloniki pilot sites.

Within the tool, a more accurate assessment of a building's environmental performance was anticipated by overwriting the provided default values (e.g., technical feasibility for element reuse, building height obtained from GIS, or material composition of building archetypes) with more precise data from project documentation. Users would also have been able to input assumptions related to dynamic parameters, such as the decarbonisation of the energy mix over time (e.g., changes in primary energy conversion factors or GHG emission factors for electricity). One of the tool's outputs would have been an Excel file containing life cycle modelling results. Users would have been responsible for assessing the representativeness and suitability of this data for integration into their bundle of tools.

The tool was intended to provide crucial information to stakeholders involved in implementing neutrality roadmaps. For example, it would have allowed quick answers to questions like: "What are the life cycle implications of replacing single-glazed windows in every building in a case study with reused double-glazed windows?" This capability was expected to facilitate the formulation and testing of circularity strategies.

However, during the first phase of the project, defining the scope of the tool proposed took longer than anticipated due to the initial level of detail proposed. This level of detail required significant effort to adapt the tool to different cities, as the calculations and simulations heavily depended on databases that were available for the Swiss case study but were difficult to scale to other cities. In this context, ETH propose to collect cities baseline information to adapt their tool and contribute to the UP2030 objectives by implementing and testing the Circular Urban Planning tool in one of the pilot sites. To achieve this, a questionnaire (see Appendix 2) was developed with the aim of gathering information about the cities' capabilities and intentions, as well as their tools.

Major finding of the questionnaire is the significant gap between LCA method application on built environment and national data on embodied flow coefficients in construction materials, with geographical coverage corresponding to UP2030 pilot cities. In this context, practitioners rely on databases available for other geographical regions. For example, Inventory of Carbon and Energy is an open-access platform developed in England, that acts as a meta-database. It is based upon a large literature review and relies on data from various sources, such as scientific literature, industry reports or environmental product declarations from different geographical regions. Thus, each coefficient has a data quality indicator that characterises number of datapoints collected. Further, Ecoinvent database is a licensed database, that is widely applied, and contains datapoints from sources including companies, industrial associations, and research institutes. Coefficients are available for one or more geographic locations, which depend on reliability and quality of collected data. Finally, other available open-access databases are process-based database KBOB in Switzerland and hybrid database combining process-based and macroeconomic input-output data EPiC database in Australia.

To achieve accurate and reliable assessment of embodied environmental flows of buildings in UP2030 pilot cities, it is critical to use context-specific and regional databases. However, due to the lack of representative data on embodied flows in construction materials, ETH recommend following the research results and relying on one of the open-access databases to test the proposed *Circular Urban Planning* tool on a pilot city neighbourhood. Such assessments would still provide valuable guidance on embodied impacts of buildings in pilot cities and inform the decision-making in the transition to carbon neutrality. When context-specific local data becomes available in the future, it will be possible to implement such national databases into the proposed tool.

Another finding is that all the respondents from pilot cities identified presence of either GIS or cadastral databases. Indeed, specific data types are needed for understanding geometrical properties of buildings and computing material inventories and spatialising the assessment results at urban scale. Moreover, further researched available data in Thessaloniki and Istanbul reported the ArcGIS software application. The specific data types searched to identify include building type, period of construction, shape (.shp) file, area, height, or number of floors. These data types are identified in Thessaloniki, more precisely, for the Kalamaria municipality, within three following websites (1) the Department of Geospatial Information- GIS of Thessaloniki, (2) GEOPYLI cartographic data (storymaps.arcgis.com) and (3) GEOPYLI of the municipality of Kalamaria (kalamaria.maps.arcgis.com). Further, some of the necessary data types are also identified in Istanbul, more precisely, at the Turkish National Geographical Information System portal and the licensed database containing some of the searched data types.

Following the questionnaire results, Thessaloniki, Lisbon, and Budapest indicated clear interest in collaborating on tool application, while Zagreb and Istanbul might be interested. Therefore, it is planned to proceed with the selection of pilot city by scheduling online meetings with city representatives to discuss in more detail possibility on gathering and accessing data for further collaboration.

3 Integration framework: Maximising the benefit from tools users

Due to the nature of the digital tools developed in the project, an integration framework was proposed with the aim of extracting the functionalities of each tool and providing added value to the agents involved in decision-making and the design of decarbonisation, energy, and climate plans. In this regard, Task 3.2 (T3.2), “Digital Twins of Urban environments for energy integration and GHG emissions reduction”, includes four digital tools intended for different purposes:

- BIM Module and LCA: Integration of construction features for the creation of standard energy consumption profiles and the design of rehabilitation plans.
- AI-Powered Toolset for the Decarbonisation of Building & Transport Solutions: Integration of energy models with renewable resources and mobility in urban environments.
- MIRA Digital Platform: Platform for visualising results and potential real-time monitoring.
- Circular Urban Planning: Development of circularity strategies through energy rehabilitation of buildings.

These tools are planned to deploy and test in Istanbul and Thessaloniki pilot site as a result of different tasks in the project within WP2 and WP4.

As these tools are intrinsically related, their combined use would allow for a comprehensive evaluation of various strategies for mitigating environmental impacts through the adoption of energy efficiency measures. As shown in Figure 2, the interconnection of the tools has been proposed to optimise different scenarios that cities can assess to prioritise actions over three-time horizons to meet the goals set by European directives: Baseline (2024), 2030, and 2050. Due of the scope-defining of the ETH tool it is not included in the framework yet.

Figure 2 Integration framework for environmental impact assessment

The development of the energy model will be executed using the GUNAM tool or the CIRCE energy module, depending on the data available from the cities. For the Istanbul case (high level of detailed data already collected as part of the efforts within the project by METU and GUNAM) and Thessaloniki or other cities (medium level of detailed data developed by CIRCE, easily scalable), slightly different approaches are established, as shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4. Subsequently, the optimisation of the proposed scenarios is based on the emissions balance in the energy district. That is, the adoption of any decarbonisation measure will have associated emissions from its implementation and execution; this balance will be calculated using the life cycle analysis model developed by CIRCE.

Flowchart information in Istanbul

- GUNAM
- CIRCE
- ETH
- MAG

Figure 3 Data exchange for Istanbul pilot site

Flowchart information in Thessaloniki

- GUNAM
- CIRCE
- ETH
- MAG

Figure 4 Data exchange for Thessaloniki pilot site

The preceding figures, Figure 3 and Figure 4, illustrate the information exchange among the different tools. In both cases, the user inputs the necessary data into the online interface (front-end), which is then stored in a database and forwarded to the calculation module developed by CIRCE where the calculations of the other tools are integrated. Once different scenarios are assessed and the most suitable one selected, the results of the analysis are sent back to the online tool to be displayed. Since the calculation modules have been developed independently, they have been designed to function as stand-alone REST APIs with an HTTPS communication protocol and an authentication method for the requests, with the aim of facilitating the exchange of information while ensuring data integrity, encryption for sharing sensitive information and guaranteeing data privacy. All necessary parameters for the relevant calculations must be entered through these APIs following JSON structured text formats.

The computational cost for assessing the GHG balance of multiple different scenarios, including simulations and inference using ML models, is relatively high. Therefore, it is expected that the response time to the user, once data has been input through the online questionnaire, will not be immediate and sometime will be needed between submitting the form and obtaining the results. To avoid resource blocking on the servers and enhance calculation flexibility alongside other tasks, the exchange of information with the front-end will be established using deferred response requests. The data will be stored internally for processing, which will be executed sequentially, although in some cases it will be possible to parallelise them in different cores. Once the results are obtained, they will be sent to the front-end, which will store them in a database to be displayed to the user.

Note: Specific structure of the JSON for data exchange within tools are being defined and could be included in this deliverable for final submission once technical partners reach an agreement on this regard (CIRCE is focusing the efforts during this month to achieve this). Also, mock-ups visualizations are proposed.

4 Scenarios proposal for Strategic Urban Planning

Within the framework of the UP2030 project, digital tools will be employed to assess various scenarios for the planning, design, and operation of districts in terms of energy and environmental considerations. These scenarios have been defined in accordance with the European directive on energy efficiency in buildings, known as the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD)(Directive (EU) 2024/1275 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 April 2024 on the Energy Performance of Buildings (Recast), 2024).

The scenarios have been formulated to simulate the changes that could be made during a renovation or improvement of a building, considering the systems that have the most significant impact on energy performance. In that sense, considering that the tools main outcomes are energy model at the building level and the Net-zero emissions balance is evaluated at the district-level, cross-cutting information that is not specific to the building constructive characteristics or geo-referencing parameters is required (e.g. electric mobility, shared energy production facilities, among others. Therefore, to evaluate the impact on energy demand as well as the environmental impact of these actions, additional data is required.

Figure 5 Net Zero Energy Balance Standards in European Union

In the next subsections, each city agent or liaison can find the data required to execute simulations.

4.1 Buildings Retrofitting

Thermal refurbishment of buildings significantly reduces energy consumption by enhancing insulation to minimise thermal transmittance. Improving the thermal envelope of a structure -using advanced insulation materials- diminishes heat loss in winter and heat gain in summer, thereby reducing the reliance on heating and cooling systems. This process involves upgrading walls, roofs, and floors with materials that have lower thermal transmittance values (U-values), ensuring better retention of internal temperatures. Such measures not only contribute to energy efficiency and lower utility bills but also support sustainability goals by reducing the overall carbon footprint of buildings.

Data required to evaluate this scenario are collected in Table 10. Desired thermal transmittance constants should be specified for each building in the pilot site. However, CIRCE could execute simulations using European standards specified in the EPBD for each Member State and defined climate zone, although this may not always be the most appropriate approach for energy efficiency considerations. In this regard, accuracy depends on the data provided for tools users.

Table 10. Data requirements for the buildings retrofitting scenario.

Retrofitting information	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit/Type
Thermal refurbishment data	<i>UwallR</i>	Thermal transmittance of the wall after renovation	W/m ² K
Thermal refurbishment data	<i>UroofR</i>	Thermal transmittance of the roof after renovation	W/m ² K
Thermal refurbishment data	<i>UwindowR</i>	Thermal transmittance of the window after renovation	W/m ² K

4.2 Integration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES)

Integration PV systems in urban environments presents a promising avenue for sustainable energy generation. With advancements in technology and design, PV panels can be seamlessly incorporated into the built environment, including rooftops, facades, and even street furniture. This integration not only enhances the aesthetic appeal of urban landscapes but also contributes significantly to renewable energy production, thereby reducing reliance on fossil fuels and mitigating carbon emissions. Furthermore, by harnessing solar energy within densely populated areas, cities can bolster their resilience to power outages and meet renewable energy targets, fostering a greener and more sustainable future.

By generating electricity on-site, buildings equipped with PV panels can offset their energy demand from the grid, thereby reducing strain during peak hours and helping to balance the overall energy load. Moreover, in the emergence of energy communities, where neighbouring buildings share energy resources and collaborate on energy management, PV installations facilitate decentralised energy production and foster community resilience. Data requirements are shown in Table 11. While PV potential is calculated by GUNAM toolset, the type of installation will be needed to execute LCA calculations and GHG emissions for installation of this technology.

Table 11. Data requirements for the Integration of RES integration

RES integration	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit/Type
PV related	<i>PV</i>	PV power installed	kW
PV related	<i>Panel</i>	Type of panel a. Single silicon b. Multi silicon	-

4.3 Integration of Storage Systems

Batteries and storage technologies are another resource used to improve the energy efficiency in buildings because of the capability for hybrid use with RES to store surpluses of energy for peak demand hours (from 17:00 to 20:00 in residential environments). Considering that the use of batteries do not involve an energy decreasing consumption, the data needed to evaluate this scenario is the type of technology that cities plan to install in districts (pilot sites) in order to estimate the environmental impact associated with the

implementation of this action (Data required are consolidated in Table 12 and it should be provided by each number of batteries in the pilot site).

Table 12. Data requirements for the Integration of Storage Systems

Storage Systems integration	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit/Type
Storage related	<i>EStorage</i>	Type of technology a. Battery Li-ion b. Battery Lead-Acid c. Battery Flow	Select option
Storage related	<i>Capacity</i>	Energy Storage Capacity	kWh

4.4 Integration of Mobility assets

This scenario is planned only for the Istanbul case because the data is already available and collected. In other cities, data collection regarding mobility assets and driver information requires a significant effort and the involvement of mobility companies, making it difficult to scale and automate.

Table 13. Data requirements for Integration of Mobility assets

Mobility assets integration	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit/Type
Mobility related	<i>DrivingInfo</i>	Driving information a. Starting point of each drive b. Ending point of each drive	m

4.5 Renovation of Energy Systems

Replacing low-performance assets reduces energy consumption and aids in the district's decarbonisation by transitioning to low-carbon technologies. For example, swapping out inefficient boilers used for heating with modern heat pumps can significantly lower energy use. Heat pumps are more energy-efficient and produce fewer carbon emissions compared to traditional boilers, thus contributing to both energy savings and a reduction in the district's overall carbon footprint. Also, electrification of the energy demand in districts can enable their participation in demand side flexibility programs. As mentioned in the previous section this replacement also involves direct GHG emissions. To evaluate that, technical specification of the assets that may be potentially renovated are required and collected in the following table.

Table 14. Data requirements for Renovation of Energy Systems

Renovation of Energy Systems	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit/Type
Energy systems related	<i>HPumpPower</i>	Heat pump power installed	kW
Energy systems related	<i>HPumpCOP</i>	Heat pump COP	-
Energy systems related	<i>BoilerPower</i>	Boiler power installed	kW
Energy systems related	<i>BoilerRate</i>	Boiler performance	%
Energy systems related	<i>Esource</i>	Type of energy source a. Electricity b. Natural gas c. Biomass Fuel oil	-
Energy systems related	<i>EER</i>	Energy Efficiency Ratio of the energy source	%

5 Next Steps

As mentioned previously, up to the date of this deliverable, the tools have been developed from different starting points and are currently in the testing and validation phase. The tools are expected to be ready for testing in relevant environments (cities) by September 2024, meeting the estimated timeline for the tested prototype milestone in February 2025. Table 15 shows a detailed Gantt chart of the activities for the second phase of the project.

Table 15. Gantt chart of the following activities proposed until the end of the task.

Partner	DoA	2024												2025						
		4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	...	12				
CIRCE	Energy module development	█																		
METU\GUNAM	Define the inputs required to assess each scenario.	█	█																	
CIRCE	Identify questionnaire questions.	█	█																	
METU\GUNAM	Define the outputs provided for each scenario.	█	█	█	█															
MAG+CIRCE	Design of the questionnaire interface.	█	█	█	█															
MAG+CIRCE	Design of the "navigation" in the tool interface and how to display the results.	█	█	█	█	█														
CIRCE	LCA module development	█	█	█	█	█	█													
METU\GUNAM	Tool energy modules development	█	█	█	█	█	█													
CIRCE \ ETH	Align efforts and potential integration - definition				█	█	█	█	█											
METU\GUNAM	API deployment for case Istanbul.								█	█										
METU\GUNAM	API deployment for case Thessaloniki.								█	█										
MAG	Implementation of the questionnaire and sending the information to CIRCE's API (Json).												█							
CIRCE	API deployment to receive interface info.												█							
CIRCE	Deployment API to request Metu\GUNAM results and send results to front-end.												█	█						
MAG	Login and user registration. User management.												█	█	█					
MAG	Implementation and deployment of the tool interface and displaying results.													█	█	█	█			
All	1st Testing and Validation														█	█	█	█		
All	Performance evaluation														█	█	█	█		
All	Tools optimisation																█	█		
All	Final version of tools																		█	

6 Barriers and Lessons Learnt

The main obstacles put particular emphasis on the challenges of digitisation and energy optimisation of buildings and transport systems.

Among the barriers are the scarcity of data and the absence of digital twins at both building and district level, which are crucial for accurate simulations and informed decision-making. In addition, the inherent complexity of urban systems complicates the coordination and implementation of context-appropriate strategies across multiple districts. Many cities also lack the digital infrastructure needed to analyse and diagnose detailed energy scenarios, hindering their ability to effectively assess and optimise energy consumption patterns. Another major challenge is the technical and logistical difficulties in integrating renewable energy systems, such as rooftop photovoltaic panels, into existing urban infrastructures. In addition, there are considerable socio-economic and policy challenges, such as local context, incentives, social factors, and regulatory frameworks, which can hinder the adoption of decarbonisation strategies. These strategies rely heavily on advanced technologies such as AI for analysis, simulation, and prediction of energy performance, which requires high levels of expertise, financing and technological readiness that may not be available.

In relation to the lessons learnt, urban decarbonisation efforts emphasize the critical need for cities to enhance their digital capabilities to thoroughly analyse energy consumption. Digital tools like BIM and LCA are invaluable for improving energy performance and planning effectively. A comprehensive strategy that integrates renewable energy, improves building insulation, and retrofits old buildings is essential. Promoting e-mobility and placing solar-powered charging stations strategically can significantly reduce emissions. It's vital for stakeholders to collaborate and develop long-term renovation plans with clear milestones set for 2030, 2040, and 2050 to meet decarbonisation and sustainability goals.

7 Conclusions

In conclusion, this deliverable provides an update on the development of the tools and the consolidation of the semantic integration framework developed under T3.2. The key findings obtained during the first phase of the project are as follows:

- ✓ The digital tools are currently in the testing phase and are expected to be fully developed by September 2024. The user manual and guidelines will be described in the second version of the deliverable “Bundle of Digital Twin Tools for Net Zero Decision-Making 2”.
- ✓ The gaps and main functionalities of each tool were considered in developing the integration framework. This includes robust energy models to assess different scenarios from GUNAM, standard hourly energy demand profiles by building type when data is lacking, building energy thermal refurbishment and life cycle assessment in the implementation phase from CIRCE, and user-friendly visualisation and monitoring capabilities (if applicable) from MAG, all aimed at providing a comprehensive digital twin at various scales for cities.
- ✓ The full development of the tools influences the technical specifications of their integration. However, communication protocols are being defined to ensure readiness when needed.
- ✓ The innovation of the tools occurs at different levels. While some cover technical aspects and improvements to tools already deployed in residential environments, others enhance the accuracy of predictive models, and some improve the relationship between models and users to provide dashboards where information is readily available and clear for decision-making purposes.

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Appendix

1. Input questionnaire for cities' data acquisition.

Bundle of digital tools survey

Within the framework of the UP2030 project, digital tools will be employed to assess various scenarios for the planning, design, and operation of districts in terms of energy and environmental considerations. These scenarios have been defined in accordance with the European directive on energy efficiency in buildings, known as the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD).

Demo site characterisation

Integration readiness level

- Do you have Digital twin/BIM from the urban district you want evaluate?

Yes/No

In case the user marks "Yes".

Please provide. format file.

In case the user marks "No", please complete the following section:

Energy Baseline characterization

In the context of positive energy districts, two tools were developed under UP2030 Project to evaluate the energy performance of buildings at different scales and addressing different levels of digital readiness and data providing availability of cities.

To execute energy-performance simulations, please fill the data needed based on the level of detailed data by building in your urban district (Pilot site).

UBTEM – Urban Building/Transport Energy Model (UBTEM)

Level of detailed data for each building/location: High

An AI powered tool for building energy retrofit PV integration in the built environment and electric micro-mobility. PED requires that urban neighbourhoods reach energy positivity by means of operationalizing several concepts in parallel. UBTEM addresses these concepts through (i) improving the energy efficiency and reducing energy demand of buildings, (ii) using high efficiency energy systems, (iii) maximizing onsite renewable energy production through rooftop PV usage in buildings. UBTEM is a decision-support tool that helps users explore different scenarios in these categories to find the most beneficial solution. Moreover, UBTEM considers electrical micro-mobility as a critical factor in decarbonisation and helps determine the optimal e-scooter charging stations as linked to buildings' PV systems, thereby helping integrate buildings, renewable energy, and e-mobility towards clean energy transition.

Data inputs:

- Building information, Geometric data (related with 3D model), material, loads etc.), semantic data (loads, insulation materials, etc.), weather information.
- PV panel characteristics, weather information.
- Electric power demand (hourly consumption), e-scooter/e-bike battery information, e-scooter/e-bike utilization information (use times, energy demand, start location, end location etc.)

Table 1. Data requirements for Model 1

	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit
Geometric Data			
	bldlayout	Footprints of building	-
	bldgheight	The height of the building	-
	zonedivision	Information about how each building is divided to zones	-
Semantic Data			
	Uwall	Thermal transmittance of wall	W/m ² K
	Uroof	Thermal transmittance of roof	W/m ² K
	Uground	Thermal transmittance of ground	W/m ² K
	Uwindow	Thermal transmittance of window	W/m ² K
	wwr _N	Window to wall ratio in north direction	%
	wwr _W	Window to wall ratio in west direction	%
	wwr _S	Window to wall ratio in south direction	%
	wwr _E	Window to wall ratio in east direction	%
	PPL	Number of people per square meter	people/m ²
	η_{boiler}	The efficiency of boiler	%
	Infiltration	The ratio of air leakage	
	SHGC	Solar heat gain coefficient of window	
	LPD	Lighting power density	W/m ²

	EPD	Equipment power density	W/m ²
	T _{heating}	The heating set point for thermostat	°C
	SE _N	The visible sky ratio from north direction (calculated from energy models)	%
	SE _W	The visible sky ratio from west direction (calculated from energy models)	%
	SE _S	The visible sky ratio from south direction (calculated from energy models)	%
	SE _E	The visible sky ratio from east direction (calculated from energy models)	%
Climate Data			
	T _{outside}	Dry bulb temperature	°C
	HDD	Heating degree days	°C
	CDD	Cooling degree days	°C
	GHR	Global horizontal radiation	W/m ²

Table 2. Data requirements for Model 2

	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit
Panel related			
	Panel_efficiency	The percentage of incident solar energy that is converted to electricity	%
	Panel_area	The area of the PV surfaces	m ²
	Age	The age of the PV panels	-
	Panel_tilt	The slope angle at which solar panels are mounted to face the sun	°
	Panel_azimuth	The angle between the projection of sun rays and a line due south or north	°
Shading related			

	Annual shading	Thermal transmittance of wall	W/m2K
Climate Data			
	Dry_bulb_aver	Average of dry bulb temperature	°C
	HDD	Heating degree days	°C
	CDD	Cooling degree days	°C
	GHR_aver	Average of global horizontal radiation	W/m2

Table 3. Data requirements for Model 3

	Abbreviation	Definition	Unit
Building related			
	Building coordinates	The coordinate points of each building	
	Qelectricity	Electricity energy consumption of buildings	kWh/m2
PV related			
	Qelecproduction	Electricity energy production from PV	kWh/m2
Mobility related			
	start_loc	The starting point of each drive	
	end_loc	The end point of each drive	

Energy assessment and Performance estimation Module (CIRCE)

Level of detailed data for each building/location: **Medium**

This tool is used to generate energy consumption profiles for buildings using minimal data, with the intention of providing decision-makers with estimates of energy consumption on a global scale. For each building, CIRCE Module use the country - technical guidelines to consider thermal performance of buildings from year of construction and estimate energy building performance.

Data inputs:

Instruction: Please fill in the following information for each building or type of buildings that may be considered "similar," as many as you have on the demonstration site.

- 1) Location:
 - a) Country
 - b) City
 - c) Coordinates
 - d) Climatic zone
- 2) Buildings data:

Each one of the options below should be able to be marked depending on how many of each building type in the pilot site.

- a) Residential
 - i) Year of construction
 - ii) Number of buildings
 - iii) Roof Area (m²)
 - iv) U_{roof} value (W/m²K)³
 - v) Window area (m²)
 - vi) U_{openings} value (W/m²K)¹
 - vii) Wall area (m²)
 - viii) U_{wall} value (W/m²K)¹
 - ix) Ground area (m²)
 - x) U_{ground} value (W/m²K)¹
- b) Other (Services/Hospitals/School...)
 - i) Year of construction
 - ii) Number of buildings
 - iii) Roof Area (m²)
 - iv) U_{roof} value (W/m²K)⁴
 - v) Window area (m²)
 - vi) U_{openings} value (W/m²K)¹

³Optional: if it is known from the Cities, but if not, it will be assumed by technical codes and specifications regarding the year of construction by European Union/Country level. However, if U is provided, demand estimation will be more accurate).

- vii) Wall area (m²)
- viii) U_{wall} value (W/m²K)¹
- ix) Ground area (m²)
- x) U_{ground} value (W/m²K)¹
- xi) Weekly schedule:
 - (1) Monday to Friday
 - (2) Monday to Sunday
 - (3) Weekends
 - (4) Other: Please specify
- xii) Opening hours
 - (1) XX: XX to XX: XX format

Renovation scenarios to evaluate decarbonization and climate mitigation of the pilot

Thermal after refurbishment of building stock

- 1) Roof U target value (W/m²K) (*If it is settled by cities, but if not, according to European requirements standards will be used although it does not mean the best energy efficiency situation)
- 2) Window /Openings U target value (W/m²K) (*Same comment as in point 1).
- 3) Wall U target value (W/m²K) (*Same comment as in point 1).
- 4) Ground U target value (W/m²K) (*Same comment as in point 1).

Energy systems renovation

1. Heating/cooling system:
 - a. Heat pump
 - i. Power installed (kW)
 - ii. COP
 - b. Boiler
 - i. Power installed (kW)
 - ii. Performance (%)
2. Type of energy source
 - a. Electricity
 - b. Natural gas
 - c. Biomass
 - d. Fuel oil.
3. Energy Efficiency Ratio

PV installation

2. PV power installed (kW)
3. Type of panel
 - a. Single silicon
 - b. Multi silicon

Mobility Integration

1. Information about drive
 - a. Starting point of each drive
 - b. Ending point of each drive

2. Building related data
 - a. Building coordinates
 - b. Electricity energy consumption of buildings

3. PV related.
 - a. Electricity energy production from PV

Energy Storage

1. Type of technology
 - a. Battery Li-ion
 - b. Battery Lead-Acid
 - c. Battery Flow

2. Capacity (kWh)

2. Circular Urban Planning questionnaire

"Circular Urban Planning" tool application on a neighbourhood case study

This questionnaire is a part of the UP2030 project carried out at ETH. The Circular Engineering for Architecture (CEA) lab's team at ETH is aiming to provide structured guidance for partner cities to assess the benefits of circular design at urban scale. The implementation of circularity strategies, such as reuse, requires us to consider available material stocks and environmental performance of buildings. Thus, we are developing "Circular Urban Planning" tool, which integrates circularity assessment and life cycle assessment (LCA) methodologies.

1. Who should answer the questionnaire?

We encourage Members of each UP2030 pilot city team, particularly those with experience or familiarity with applying life cycle assessment (LCA) method on any scale of built environment, ranging from materials to cities.

2. What is the aim of the questionnaire?

The aim of this questionnaire is to explore the conditions for LCA method application on a neighbourhood case study in UP2030 pilot cities. The analysis of the questionnaire results is expected to inform the selection of a partner city, that is interested in collaborating and applying the Circular Urban Planning tool on one of its neighbourhoods.

3. Why should you participate in this questionnaire?

Your participation will contribute to our research project aiming to inform decision-making process towards improving circularity at urban scale in your UP2030 pilot city.

Estimated time for completing this survey is up to 8 minutes.

If you are interested in the results of the survey, please write your email address at the end of the questionnaire. We will send you analysis report with the results in a few months.

Thank you and kind regards,
Katarina

Katarina Slavkovic

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6 Responses

Closed Status

1. What is your Name and SURNAME?

6 Responses

2. Which institution are you affiliated with?

6 Responses

3. What is your UP2030 pilot city?

6 Responses

4. What is your occupation?

● Architect/Designer	1
● Engineer	1
● Sustainability consultant	1
● Urban Designer	0
● Urban Planner	1
● City Representative	2
● Academic	0
● Researcher	0
● Other	0

5. If "Academic" (e.g. Professor), or "Researcher" (e.g. Postdoc, PhD, Scientific Assistant), please specify your position and field of expertise

0 Responses

Latest Responses

6. If "Other", please specify your position and field of expertise

0
Responses

Latest Responses

7. Have you ever assessed life cycle environmental performance of a built asset (such as a building, transport infrastructure, open space) at any scale of built environment (from material to urban scale)?

- Yes 2
- No 4

8. What was the spatial scale of your assessment?

- Material (e.g. wood, concrete, st... 1
- Assembly (e.g. structural system... 0
- Built asset (e.g. building, road, p... 1
- Portfolio of assets (groups of bu... 0
- Neighbourhood 0
- City 0

9. Which method did you use for the assessment of environmental impacts?

- LCA-based software 2
- Regulations and norms 0
- Design guidelines 0
- Another construction project as ... 0
- Formulas (e.g. in Excel) 0
- Rules of thumb 0
- Other 1

10. If "Other", please specify the method

1
Responses

Latest Responses

"Completed a study on LCA and LCC assessment of building and road constr..."

11. Which database of embodied flow coefficients have you used for the assessment?

2
Responses

Latest Responses

"We don't have information, but we are in partnership with experts who are ..."

12. Are you familiar with other databases of environmental flow coefficients available in your country? Please write the name of the database (e.g. Ecoinvent; Inventory of Carbon and Energy; etc.)

2
Responses

Latest Responses

"We don't have information, but we are in partnership with experts who are ..."

13. Are you familiar with life cycle assessment (LCA) method application on built environment?

● Yes 0
● No 4

14. Are you familiar with embodied environmental flows associated with the built environment? (e.g. greenhouse gas emissions associated with material production processes; energy use during use of a building)

● Yes 3
● No 1

15. Are you familiar with databases of environmental flow coefficients available in your country? If "Yes", please write the name of the database (e.g. Ecoinvent; Inventory of Carbon and Energy; etc.)

2
Responses

Latest Responses

"Inventory of Carbon and Energy"

16. Have you ever used geographic information system (GIS) databases in your pilot city or your country?

● Yes 5
● No 1

17. Please specify the name(s) of the database(s):

5
Responses

Latest Responses
 "Kommonitor, Open data Stadt Münster"
 "point cloud, ArcGIS"
 "Public (ex. Copernicus, KSH - Central Statistical Office) and private database..."

18. Are you familiar with GIS databases available in your pilot city? - If yes, please specify the name(s) of the database(s):

1
Responses

Latest Responses

19. Have you ever used cadastral data for buildings available in your pilot city?

● Yes 4
 ● No 2

20. Please specify the name of the database:

4
Responses

Latest Responses
 "building locations, roof sizes etc. "
 "ex. Lechner Knowledge Center"

21. Are you familiar with cadastral data for buildings available in you pilot city?

● Yes 0
 ● No 2

22. Are you interested in collaborating with the Circular Engineering for Architecture (CEA) team, on testing the Circular Urban Planning tool on a case study neighbourhood in your partner city?

● Yes 3
 ● No 1
 ● Other 2

23. If Other, please specify (e.g. before making a decision, I would like to get more information / schedule an online meeting / consult with my group, etc.).

2
Responses

Latest Responses
"schedule an online miting and consult with my group."

24. If you would like to receive the results of this survey, please confirm your e-mail address so we can share our analysis report. Thank you!

6
Responses
